
COLLECTING THE WEST: REIMAGINING WESTERN AUSTRALIA FROM ITS COLLECTIONS

AUSTRALIAN RESEARCH COUNCIL LINKAGE PROGRAM GRANT LP160100078

Collections Report: Bristol Museum & Art Gallery

Australian Government

Australian Research Council

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**WESTERN
AUSTRALIA**

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WAM WESTERN
AUSTRALIAN
MUSEUM

State Library
OF WESTERN AUSTRALIA

The British
Museum

This **Collections Report** is one of a series of reports produced by:

**Collecting the West: Reimagining Western Australia
from its collections**

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Authors:

Siti Ridhuan, Toby Burrows, Alistair Paterson

(University of Western Australia)

Andrea Witcomb (Deakin University)

Published by:

School of Social Sciences, University of Western Australia, 2023

PROJECT SUMMARY

The *Collecting the West: Reimagining Western Australia From its Collections* project was funded by the Australian Research Council (ARC) Linkage Program (LP160100078). The project is managed by the University of Western Australia in association with the Alfred Deakin Centre for Citizenship and Globalisation at Deakin University. The project partner organisations are the Western Australian Museum, the State Library of Western Australia and the Art Gallery of Western Australia, together with our international partner, the British Museum.

One aspect of the project involved creating a database of collections of specimens in various select institutions. The database provided a shared platform for project investigators to reveal trends and relationships in collecting histories. The platform for database is Nodegoat -- a web-based data management, network analysis, and visualisation environment developed by LAB1100 in The Hague.

We provide here an overview of the collections in Bristol Museum & Art Gallery from Western Australia. This list may not be complete, however it may provide a useful tool to better understand how Western Australia fits in Bristol Museum & Art Gallery history.

BRISTOL MUSEUM & ART GALLERY

AT A GLANCE

Entity types

Agents

Acquisition Activity

Locations

Geographic Visualisation

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